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Analysis of Management in the Practice of Ecomarketing and Ecotourism Company in the Development of Ecotourism

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***Abstract.** Ecotourism marketing also has its own characteristics. METH, travel agencies, associations offer their (unique) tourist products and services to consumers.*

In the marketing programs of protected natural areas (METX), attractiveness and uniqueness of goods and services, types and directions of recreation and their definition are given.

***Keywords:** tourism, service, marketing, tour operator, ecotourism.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism marketing is a system of continuous coordination of offered services with services demanded in the market. In doing so, tourism enterprises bring services to a level that is profitable for them and implement effective remuneration of employees than competitors.

Ecotourism marketing is not a separate activity and movement, but a complex of them. It is an integrated system that consists of combining and integrating the promotion and sale of services or the production of services. He always looks forward to the future, looking for opportunities to adapt and implement profit-enhancing tools.

Due to the mutuality of benefits and interests, ecotourism marketing begins with the usefulness of the main product and ends with the formation of packaging (packaging), price, information, sales and image, and various marketing techniques, and then leads to the improvement of the physical and psychological mood of the buyer, as well as the increase in the desire to consume this product.

In this regard, eco-tourism marketing solves the following two principle issues in the field of ecotourism: 1) it helps to increase the potential of purchasing products by improving the utility of products and achieving the appropriate results; 2) improves the mood of their perception, understanding, evaluation.

At the heart of modern marketing approaches is the environmental acceptability of the product at all stages of the product's life cycle (from production to processing of its waste).

In ecotourism in general, ecomarketing is involved in balancing the economic and environmental interests of the ecotourism enterprise, and assumes certain social responsibilities in this regard.

In ecotourism, the goal of ecomarketing is to direct consumer behavior by increasing the ecological usefulness of products and services or by increasing consumer perception of this usefulness (for example, with the help of advertising).

Determining the ecomarketing strategy in ecotourism consists of drawing up long-term plans of consumer behavior in relation to the market, competition, time, both at the initial stage of the enterprise's activity, and to support its successful development.

From this point of view, we believe that the main directions of effective use of ecomarketing in the management of ecotourism development in Uzbekistan in the future should be as follows:

Organization of the set of goods and services offered in the ecotourism market based on their precise definition and consideration of consumer demand. In this case, it is necessary to identify the group of consumers interested in "green" ecotourism product services, to study and evaluate their reactions (attitudes) to the company's offers, and to determine and implement directions for influencing them. These allow for a much wider range of consumer interests and preferences.

In order to achieve success in competition, occupying the ecotourism market and places on the basis of coordination (differentiation) of the offered ecotourism products and goods with demand. In this case, through greening of goods and services, it is possible to increase the tendency of consumers to relatively more expensive, but ecologically acceptable and safe goods and services, and to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise.

Achieving leadership by introducing new products and services with ecological properties to the market. This direction is associated with a lot of time, high cost of development, high market risks, and at the same time, it provides an opportunity to get a large income and to have the image of a responsible environmental enterprise in the long term.

Good knowledge of market characteristics and, accordingly, wide application of ecomarketing are important conditions for successful development of ecotourism in METHs. Effective use of ecomarketing indicators is important. We believe that it is appropriate to use the following groups of ecomarketing indicators specific to ecotourism:

- economic indicators: price, warranty conditions, additional services, service conditions;
- socio-ecological indicators: service delivery, definition of the workplace taking into account environmental safety, impact of services, production, consumption processes on environmental protection, energy consumption in the use of consumer goods, impact on public health;
- functional indicators: fields of application, suitability for consumption, service life, structures;
- aesthetic indicators: nature, biodiversity, landscape and value of materials, quality of design. Also, indicators taken into account in eco-marketing include eco-marking, advertising information indicators.

New instruments and forms of ecomarketing are increasingly being used in modern ecomarketing, including ecotourism marketing. These include eco-sponsoring, eco-tainment, eco-leasing, etc., which are starting to be used in foreign countries.

Eco-sponsoring means mutual cooperation of a company and environmental organizations in a certain form. The company expects a positive image transfer from sponsorship activities, that is, it hopes that the positive image of environmental organizations will be transferred to the sponsor. The organization can use the sponsorship funds for the implementation of specific ecotourism projects.

Eco-entertainment (derived from the words Ecology and Entertainment, which means establishing relations with consumers through a new communication concept) is based on the establishment of "entertainment centers" (instead of shopping centers). In such centers, the buyer not only buys some goods, but also becomes a participant in the entertainment process, feels the entertainment complex, which can end with a purchase. This is one of the types of "environmental propaganda".

Eco-leasing means giving the right to temporarily use certain investment objects on the basis of payment. In this case, the right to own property is not given, on this basis, the processes of production, consumption and disposal of the product are carried out.

When using these new forms in Uzbekistan, the specific features of ecotourism should be taken into account. In the ecotourism development management system, advertising plays an important role in establishing informational relationships between ecotourism organizations and their external environment. Advertising promotes the strengths of ecotourism products and services, and this helps to increase the flow of consumers. Advertising promotes changes in the usefulness and environmental quality of new goods and services offered.

Wide use of the following types of tourism advertising in the practice of managing the development of ecotourism in our country is becoming an objective necessity:

1. Press (newspapers, directories, guidebooks, magazines) advertisements. In it, ecotourism operators advertise in special publications (magazines and newspapers covering nature and active recreation opportunities), road signs describing ecological trails of buffer zones of protected areas are published and they are updated annually. Hundreds of thousands of tourists and professionals will benefit from the information provided in press advertisements. METHs of Uzbekistan, first of all, biosphere reserves and national parks should be advertised in this direction.

2. Advertising on television (advertising-informational video films, commercials, etc.). This is the most expensive and prestigious, and at the same time the most popular type of advertising.

3. Advertising on the radio. Most tourism companies use radio advertising as an additional tool to other main advertising media.

4. Visual advertising. It advertises information about the region, protected areas, their flora and fauna, exquisite landscapes, ecotourism routes and programs in print or by hand using paper and banners.

5. Advertisements will be sent to citizens' homes and relevant professionals by mail. Sale of goods through catalogs, home delivery, distribution of booklets, brochures, postcards, prospectuses, advertising leaflets in hotels, resorts, holiday homes, airlines is carried out through postal advertising.

It is also important to prepare and distribute booklets with maps, drawings, road signs, photo albums, eco-references, leaflets with pictures of birds, plants, animals, color photos and notes of METHs and ecotourism routes. They are necessary means of awareness of ecology and formation of environmental culture in society.

6. Advertising on consumer goods wrapping papers, bags. They are a very effective tool for advertising public goods, ecotourism services or a travel agency in general. Souvenir products, shirts, pens, calendars, gifts, etc., with symbols of national parks, natural monuments, etc., are of great importance in the promotion of ecological travel, and their wide use in practice is extremely important.

7. Writing by rotating electronic boards and illuminated texts. Usually at night in the central streets and squares, in theaters, advertising of eco-tours and goods necessary for tourists should become a permanent event.

8. Verbal advertising method in personal communication and telephone conversation. Advertising through the Internet site is necessary. All over the world network advertising has started to play an increasingly significant role. Many eco-tourism organizations, reserves and national parks have their own websites on the Internet, where they describe the proposed routes.

In terms of effectiveness of tourism advertising abroad, advertising directly through the Internet is in the first place, publications specifically for tourists are in the second place, and television is in the third place. Many tourist companies with sufficient funds prefer to advertise in the press, television, radio, such advertising is especially effective in the run-up to the tourist season.

Advertising affects human emotions, resulting in a certain desire. This scheme of "perception - influence - emergence of desire" is becoming one of the important factors in the development of ecotourism.

Thus, the wide use of eco-management and eco-marketing approaches in ecological tourism serves as the main instrument for increasing the competitiveness of eco-tourism products and services in the domestic and international market and increasing the efficiency of managing the development of eco-tourism activities.

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